

Google Pixel 3 Setup documentation

Date of Setup: 20th April 2025

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First: Basic Settings

No differences

- Language Settings (English standard, no change)
- Vision settings (no changes made to standard)
- Emergency call option

Continuing with „Start“

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Asked for Sim-Card and Mobile Network

No differences

- Pressing „Skip“

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Connect to WiFi & Copy apps, data

No differences

- Second documentation was connected to internet chose HHU-Gast as Wi-Fi network and signed via student account
- Third documentation was connected to a local Red

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Setting up new Google Account

- Setting up a new Google account – „create account“ (for personal use):

Name: Dice

Gender: Rather not say

Birthday: 25th April 2000

E-Mail: dicephoneproject2401@gmail.com

Password: Dice24.01

Asked to add phone number: Decline

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Additional settings: Manual

- Web activity: Keep
 - YouTube History: Keep
 - Ad personalization: Show personalized ads
 - Get occasional privacy reminders: No
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- Change in the title of step 1 “For faster searching...” to “For more personalised experiences...”
 - And step 2 “For YouTube homepage recommendations...” to “For more tailored YouTube recommendations...”

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Additional settings: Manual

No differences

- Ad personalisation: Show personalised ads
- Get occasional privacy reminders: No

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Privacy and Terms

No differences

- I agree
- Find pdf of privacy policy (download not immediately possible) and terms & conditions attached with presentation

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The screenshot shows the Google Privacy and Terms page. It features the Google logo at the top, followed by the title "Privacy and Terms". The main content is divided into several paragraphs explaining the terms of service and privacy policy. A list of bullet points details various services and features. At the bottom, there are two buttons: "Don't create the account" and "I agree".

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Date & Time

- Entering correct data
- For third documentation it was not necessary to adjust Date & Time

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The screenshot shows the 'Date & time' settings interface. At the top, there is a blue calendar icon and the text 'Date & time' with the instruction 'Adjust if needed.' Below this, there are three settings sections, each with a dropdown arrow on the right: 'Berlin GMT+01:00', 'Date Wed, Jan 24, 2024', and 'Time 4:38 PM'. At the bottom right, there is a blue button labeled 'Next'. A back arrow is visible at the bottom left of the screen.

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Google Services

No differences

- Backup to Google Drive
- Use location
- Allow scanning
- Diagnostic Data

All agreed to

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Screenlock

No differences

- Fingerprint: Skip
- Code set to 1234 (no Screenshot taken)

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Continue Setup?

No differences

- Google Assistant: Turn on
- Voice Match: No thanks (Screenshot missing)
- Squeeze: Do it later
- Google Pay: Skip
- Always on display: Notifications added to lockscreen (Screenshot missing)
- Anything else: No thanks
- Last tips: All set

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Home Screen

- Visible apps on home screen
 - There was no option to pick a (different) browser
 - Google search bar
 - There was no option to pick a (different) search engine
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- Third documentation has not Google Pay neither Wallet app in the recommended apps.

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First Google Search

No differences

- Search for „dice hhu“

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First use of browser (google chrome)

No differences

- Agree to terms and conditions – accept all
- Signing in with google account
- Google as standard search engine
- Recommendations for: Facebook, YouTube, Amazon, Wikipedia, ESPN, Yahoo, Ebay and Instagram
- No other browsers but products from other companies

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Google play store

- Get started: Linking Google services
- Third documentation it is find the message of new EU laws omitting the date (March 6th)
- In the apart of “what's not changing?” It is find a new paragraph: “Data can be shared to effectively help you complete tasks. For example. If you make a purchase on Google Play and Googles payment service will share related info....”

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Google play store

- New apps are suggested (Sponsored). For example, Wolt, Crunchyroll

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List of default apps

No differences

- Google Chrome, Google Pay, Google assistant → preinstalled
 - No alternatives offered

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Third Documentation
20th April 2024

Setting up Gmail

- Dice E-Mail already installed
- Option: Add new E-Mails from different providers
- Third documentation present changes in the steps to switch or find all messages from your email accounts.

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Trying to download an app outside the play store

No differences

- Download through chip.de
- Allowing Chrome to access files
- Downloading Fortnite Installer
 - This can harm your device, download anyway? → Continue

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Comparison with prior setup in January

- Connection to Student Wi-Fi was possible (slide 4)
 - Changes in the Title of 2/4 setting step (slide 6)
 - No option to adjust date and time (slide 9)
 - No Wallet app icon neither Google Pay icon in the principal screen (slide 13)
 - Change in the first paragraph and addition of other one referring to EU legislation (slide 16)
 - New design in the Option to add E-Mail addresses from different providers (slide 19)
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- There is not changes in the offer of Browser, Voice Assistance, Mail, Pay method.